

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF INTERLACED-PREPREG CLOTH

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses interlaced-prepreg cloth, a new material format which provides all the manufacturing advantages of cloth while retaining the structural integrity of unidirectional prepreg. Interlaced-prepreg is a type of cloth made by a machine that interlaces ribbons obtained by slitting prepreg tape. Experimental work was conducted in which the specific objective was to structurally characterize the cloth by determining four elastic constants and five strength constants, as required by laminated plate theory and the quadratic failure criterion. The experimental results indicate that, for tensile modulus, tensile strength and compressive strength, the [0/90]_s, [0/90/+45/-45]_s, and [+45/-45]_s laminates made of interlaced-prepreg cloth compare very closely with the equivalent laminates made of unidirectional prepreg.

INTRODUCTION

Unidirectional prepreg is used in nearly all advanced composite applications that require structural integrity. Due to high use, good quality control on prepreg manufacture has become standard. However, there are a few manufacturing disadvantages inherent with a prepreg format. Prepreg, generally made in only 12 inch wide strips, is cumbersome to use in some applications. Handling is further complicated because unidirectional prepreg is susceptible to splitting.

Cloth is an easy-to-use alternative to prepreg and has been around for many years. In addition to flexibility in size, cloth allows for greater ease in handling. Draping is easier, making mold manufacturing easier. An added advantage of the fabric form is the cross-weave which provides an inherent crack arresting configuration. Although there are many forms of cloth available, cloth has been limited to structurally insignificant applications because of its only marginal performance as a structural material.

This paper discusses interlaced-prepreg cloth, Quadrax[®], a new material format which provides all the manufacturing advantages of cloth while retaining the structural integrity of unidirectional prepreg. This new material format is a type of cloth made by a machine that interlaces ribbons obtained by slitting thermoplastic prepreg tape. A schematic of the resulting interlaced prepreg is shown in Figure 1. Specifically, four inch wide prepreg is slit into either 1/4, 3/16, 3/8 or 1/2 inch wide ribbon. The 3/16 inch wide ribbon was used in the materials for this test program. The ribbon is interlaced by a proprietary machine into a seamless tube of five satin harness cloth. Depending on how the woven tube is then split open, the layup of the broadgoods can be 0/90 or +45/-45 or any other set of right angles. This is a generic process that can be applied to different fiber and matrix systems. It is best limited to thermoplastics, however, because the presence of tack in thermosets complicates the slitting and interlacing process.

FIGURE 1 SCHEMATIC OF INTERLACED-PREPREG CLOTH.

Experimental work was conducted in which the specific objective was to confirm ideas indicating that this interlaced-prepreg cloth material shows superior material properties to that of other cloth forms. The specific objective was to structurally characterize this new material format by determining four elastic constants and five strength constants, as required by laminated plate theory and the quadratic failure criterion. At least nine material properties are necessary to realistically characterize the structural behavior of a composite. In constructing a test program, the emphasis was on consistency. Several material systems were considered in order to isolate material from format characteristics. Although not discussed in this paper, a few fatigue tests were included to complement the static strength testing. The failure modes were examined both macro- and microscopically to insure a reasonable understanding and accurate assessment of the material behavior.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Five cloth material systems were investigated as summarized in Table 1. An intermediate modulus carbon, E-glass and Kevlar 49 were the fibers investigated. The carbon fiber was tested in two different thermoplastic matrices and also in hybrid form with the glass fiber. Subsequently, laminates made of the unidirectional tape of the two carbon fiber systems were also tested as listed in Table 1.

Some of the laminates were consolidated at the USAF Materials Laboratory and some were provided preconsolidated by Phillips Petroleum. A summary of the key processing parameters for the panels fabricated at the Materials Lab is also included in Table 1.

TABLE 1 PROCESSING INFORMATION

FORMAT	FIBER	MATRIX	PROCESSING	COMMENTS
cloth	AS4	PEEK	720F, 200psi, 45min	
cloth	AS4	PPS	(by Phillips)	
cloth	AS4 & E-gl	PPS	(by Phillips)	
cloth	E-glass	PPS	(by Phillips)	
cloth	Kevlar 49	PPS	625F, 150psi, 5min	Dry out plies in 300F oven for 2 hours.
UD	AS4	PEEK	720F, 200psi, 45min	
UD	AS4	PPS	650F, 200psi, 5min	Insert into hot press; cool as quickly as possible.

Design of the test specimens is based on ASTM Standards. Due to a limited supply of material, deviation in some of the dimensions was necessary. As the test program evolved into the evaluation of other material combinations, the same specimen dimensions and test techniques were used in order to provide a basis for comparison. The specimens dimensions, although deviating slightly from ASTM standards, are believed to provide reliable and accurate data and not just a qualitative comparison, owing to the fact that the essence of the specimen standards was unchanged.

Figure 2 summarizes the specimen dimensions. The laminates were generally made of the equivalent of 16 plies, which in the case of the cloth amounts to eight layers (since each layer of cloth is composed of two interlaced plies).

Mechanical testing was accomplished on a Materials Testing System (MTS Model #810.14A) axial load machine. Hydraulically operated wedge action grips (MTS Model #645.12A-03), tensile rated at 50,000 lb, were used to insure a secure grip. Tensile strengths and tensile moduli are determined as outlined by ASTM D3039. To monitor strain, 0/90 strain gage rosettes were mounted centrally on one face of each tensile specimen. The system is operated in load control mode. All tension testing is conducted with a ramp input controlling the crosshead motion typically at a speed of 0.02 in/in/min.

FIGURE 2 SUMMARY OF SPECIMEN DIMENSIONS IN INCHES: (a) TENSION TEST SPECIMEN; (b) SIDE-SUPPORTED COMPRESSION TEST SPECIMEN

Two to five replications were completed of each test. Four stiffness constants and five strength constants were determined from static testing. Transverse tensile strength specimens were tested without bonded tabs in order to remove the stress concentration.

In-plane shear properties were determined by tension testing a $[\pm 45]$ specimen as outlined by ASTM D3518. The shear tensile strength was determined as one half the tensile strength of a $[\pm 45]$ specimen. The shear stiffness, E_s , can be computed as shear strength (one half the axial tensile strength of $[\pm 45]$ specimen) divided by the shear strain (axial strain minus tangential strain).

Compressive strength testing was conducted using a dogbone specimen. Similar to ASTM D395 tensile specimen, the dogbone specimen is tapered inward to control the failure location. The faces are side-supported. Differing from an end-loaded compression test specimen, a side load is introduced to the specimen by the tabs. The gage length is sufficiently long to neglect edge effects due to the specimen tabs. The compressive testing is conducted with a ramp input controlling the crosshead motion typically at a speed of 0.01 in/in/min.

RESULTS

Table 2a summarizes test data for the interlaced-prepreg cloth laminates. Table 2b summarizes test data for unidirectional laminates. The strength and modulus values are based upon the average of three to six specimens. One simple conclusion that can be made from Table 2a is that the properties of the $[0/90]_s$ and $[90/0]_s$ laminates are very similar, indicating that the structural properties are independent of the cloth warp and fill directions.

The results shown in Tables 2a and 2b can be most easily interpreted by graphing specific parameters. One comparison would be to directly relate the $[0]_s$ unidirectional behavior to that of the $[0/90]_s$ cloth laminates, recognizing that the cloth has only 50% of the fibers in the longitudinal direction as compared to the unidirectional laminate. In Figure 3a, the tensile and compressive strengths are compared side-by-side for a unidirectional laminate and a interlaced-prepreg cloth laminate for AS4/PEEK material. In Figure 3b, AS4/Ryton is compared similarly.

From the graphs in Figure 3, it can be observed that the cloth attains well over 50 percent of the structural baseline properties demonstrated by the unidirectional prepreg. Furthermore from Figure 3, it can be observed that the interlaced-prepreg format demonstrates a compressive strength with a significantly higher percentage of the tensile strength than the unidirectional laminate. Although some unidirectional compression specimens displayed shearout failure, the compressive strength values were confirmed by IITRI test specimens.

TABLE 2 SUMMARY OF STATIC DATA FOR (a) INTERLACED-PREPREG CLOTH LAMINATES; (b) UNIDIRECTIONAL PREPREG LAMINATES

Product form	cloth	cloth	cloth	cloth	cloth
Fiber	AS4	AS	AS&Glass	Glass	Kev49
Matrix	PEEK	Ryton	Ryton	Ryton	Ryton
[0/90]4s					
Tensile modulus, (Msi)	10.26	8.80	6.09	3.89	4.32
	<i>±0.28</i>	<i>±0.64</i>	<i>±0.06</i>	<i>±0.10</i>	<i>±0.05</i>
Poisson's ratio	0.03	0.01	0.07	0.12	0.04
	<i>±0.011</i>	<i>±0.028</i>	<i>±0.025</i>	<i>±0.005</i>	<i>±0.006</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	155.1	111.0	87.2	49.6	56.4
	<i>±4.4</i>	<i>±5.4</i>	<i>±3.6</i>	<i>±2.2</i>	<i>±3.6</i>
Compression str., (ksi)	98.9	60.1	49.8	49.0	22.4
	<i>±0.5</i>	<i>±7.7</i>	<i>±0.8</i>	<i>±7.4</i>	<i>±1.4</i>
[90/0]4s					
Tensile modulus, (Msi)	10.26	8.48	5.93	3.87	4.34
	<i>±0.48</i>	<i>±0.25</i>	<i>±0.17</i>	<i>±0.02</i>	<i>±0.26</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	157.4	108.5	83.3	53.6	48.1
	<i>±11.1</i>	<i>±4.5</i>	<i>±4.7</i>	<i>±0.7</i>	<i>±3.9</i>
Compression str., (ksi)	96.6	64.4	45.6	55.2	27.6
	<i>±10.4</i>	<i>±2.7</i>	<i>±3.4</i>	<i>±3.4</i>	<i>±1.3</i>
[+45/-45]4s					
Lam. ten. mod., (Msi)	0.88	0.31	0.25	0.28	0.19
	<i>±0.06</i>	<i>±0.09</i>	<i>±0.03</i>	<i>±0.05</i>	<i>±0.02</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	43.5	19.4	11.3	9.3	14.4
	<i>±6.8</i>	<i>±2.7</i>	<i>±0.3</i>	<i>±0.3</i>	<i>±0.1</i>
[0/90,+45/-45]2s					
Tensile modulus, (Msi)	6.49	5.80	-	-	3.82
	<i>±0.79</i>	<i>±0.31</i>			<i>±0.25</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	103.0	68.1	-	-	35.5
	<i>±8.5</i>	<i>±0.8</i>			<i>±0.6</i>
Compression str., (ksi)	77.0	44.0	-	-	-
Fiber volume, (%)	60.6	52.4	54.3	54.2	48.5
Ply thickness, (in)	0.0095	0.012	0.012	0.013	0.012

* Italicized values indicate standard deviation in absolute units

Product form	UD	UD
Fiber	AS4	AS4
Matrix	PEEK	Ryton
[0]8s		
Tensile modulus, (Msi)	19.78	16.83
	<i>±0.08</i>	<i>±0.23</i>
Poisson's ratio	0.28	0.35
	<i>±0.02</i>	<i>±0.03</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	260.4	207.9
	<i>±9.6</i>	<i>±0.65</i>
Compression str., (ksi)	127.0	88.7
	<i>±5.1</i>	<i>±0.4</i>
[90]8s		
Tensile modulus, (Msi)	1.47	1.98
	<i>±0.04</i>	<i>±0.07</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	13.6	4.0
	<i>±0.2</i>	<i>±0.4</i>
Compression str., (ksi)	38.7	23.0
	<i>±3.6</i>	<i>±1.1</i>
[0,90]4s		
Tensile modulus, (Msi)	9.75	7.99
	<i>±0.44</i>	<i>±0.07</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	152.8	110.3
	<i>±5.2</i>	<i>±4.5</i>
Compression str., (ksi)	103.5	62.7
	<i>±2.6</i>	<i>±1.9</i>
[±45]4s		
Lam. ten. mod., (Msi)	0.85	0.43
	<i>±0.01</i>	<i>±0.02</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	53.1	18.5
	<i>±3.0</i>	<i>±1.3</i>
Compression str., (ksi)	35.5	19.2
	<i>±1.2</i>	<i>±1.4</i>
[0,90,45,-45]2s		
Tensile modulus, (Msi)	7.32	7.44
	<i>±0.09</i>	<i>±2.52</i>
Tensile strength, (ksi)	106.7	80.9
	<i>±2.3</i>	<i>±0.6</i>
Compression str., (ksi)	84.8	58.5
	<i>±1.3</i>	<i>±2.3</i>
Fiber vol., (%)	62.3	55.9
Ply thickness, (in)	0.0050	0.0060

* Italicized values indicate standard deviation in absolute units.

From the results of Figure 3, it appears that there is very good fiber property translation and no penalty is being paid for the cloth format. However, the cloth exhibits more than can be accounted for by the fiber contribution due to the percentage of 0 degree plies. The simplified rationalization of ignoring the structural contribution of the 90 degree plies, which is the basis of netting analysis, is inadequate. In order to account for the synergistic effects of 0 degree and 90 degree layers, laminated plate theory must be used. Along with the issue of fiber property translation, it is unclear how much of the relative improvement in compressive strength is due to the synergistic effects or due to the interlaced cloth format. For a better interpretation of experimental data, the interlaced-prepreg cloth laminates should be compared to equivalent unidirectional prepreg laminates.

FIGURE 3 STRENGTH COMPARISON OF INTERLACED-PREPREG CLOTH AND UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES

Figures 4 and 5 provide a side-by-side comparison of laminates made of interlaced-prepreg cloth and the equivalent laminates made of unidirectional prepreg. Figure 4a evaluates the tensile modulus of three sets of AS4/PEEK laminates (a bidirectional [0,90]s, a quasi-isotropic [0,90,+45,-45]s, and a bidirectional [+45,-45]s) for the two material formats (laminates made of interlaced-prepreg cloth and of unidirectional prepreg). Figure 4b evaluates the tensile and compressive strengths. Figures 5a and 5b similarly show the tensile modulus and strengths results, respectively, for equivalent laminates made of AS4/Ryton.

FIGURE 4 MODULUS AND STRENGTH COMPARISON OF AS4/PEEK INTERLACED-PREPREG CLOTH LAMINATES AND AN EQUIVALENT LAMINATES MADE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL PREPREG.

FIGURE 5 MODULUS AND STRENGTH COMPARISON OF AS4/Ryton INTERLACED-PREPREG CLOTH LAMINATES AND AN EQUIVALENT LAMINATES MADE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL PREPREG.

From Figure 4 and 5, it can be observed that the interlaced-prepreg cloth compares very closely (in general, within 10 percent) to the results of [0,90]s, [0,90,+45,-45]s and [+45,-45]s laminates made of unidirectional prepreg for tensile modulus and for tensile and compressive strengths. These results confirm that no penalty is paid for cloth format.

Figure 6 is a comparison of the interlaced-prepreg cloth structural properties exhibited by a hybrid laminate and that of both the constituent materials. The hybrid laminate is made up of interlaced-prepreg plies having carbon in the longitudinal direction and glass in the transverse direction. These plies are alternated during the layup such that a balance between the two fibers is achieved in both directions. Figure 6 is useful for examining the material effect on the structural property behavior of interlaced-prepreg cloth. Figure 6a shows the tensile modulus of two bidirectional laminates. Figure 6b enables a comparison of tensile and compressive strengths.

From Figure 6, it can be observed that with the exception of the compressive strength, the hybrid laminate performs in proportion to its constituents. These results indicate that the structural performance of interlaced-prepreg cloth is independent of material.

FIGURE 6 MODULUS AND STRENGTH COMPARISON OF THREE MATERIAL SYSTEMS OF INTERLACED-PREPREG LAMINATES: AS/Ryton, AS&E-GLASS/Ryton, AND E-GLASS/Ryton.

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results lead to several conclusions. The strength and stiffness properties in the longitudinal and transverse directions of the interlaced-prepreg cloth have been established as equal. Good fiber property translation and improved compressive strength relative to the tensile strength was obtained by the cloth laminates with respect to unidirectional prepreg tape, due to the interlaced-prepreg cloth format as well as synergistic effects. Laminated plate theory should be used to accurately assess the behavior of laminates. A direct comparison of equivalent laminates made of cloth and made of unidirectional prepreg indicates equal structural property performance. Finally, since interlaced-prepreg cloth has been compared with prepreg for a number of materials, the structural behavior is independent of material properties and validates rule-of-mixtures predictions in the case of hybrid materials.

A complete set of static test data as used by laminated plate theory and the quadratic failure criterion has been established. The ease of manufacturing with structurally sound cloths is finally made possible as a consequence of a new material processing technique. Interlaced-prepreg is a viable solution to the search for cloth with structural integrity.

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